

Contamination of Agricultural Soils by Toxic Trace Metals in an Industrial District in Vietnam

**Thin Nguyen Van^{1*}, Akinori Ozaki², Yiping Xie³, Anh Nguyen Duc⁴
and Kiyoshi Kurosawa²**

¹Graduate School of Integrated Science for Global Society, Kyushu University, Fukuoka, 819-0395, Japan.

²Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Kyushu University, Fukuoka, 812-8581, Japan.

³Graduate School of Social and Cultural Studies, Kyushu University, Fukuoka 819-0395, Japan.

⁴Soil Science Laboratory, Faculty of Land Management, Vietnam National University of Agriculture, Hanoi, Vietnam.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author TNV designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author AO assisted the analyses of the study. Authors YX and AND assisted the field sampling and managed the literature searches. Author KK provided laboratory equipment in Japan and revised the final version of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/JGEESI/2017/33235

Editor(s):

(1) Mohamed Nageeb Rashed, Department of Chemistry, Aswan University, Egypt.

Reviewers:

(1) El-Sayed Ewis Omran, Suez Canal University, Egypt.

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(4) Jerome Desire Aliebakaa Kpan, Coburg University, Germany.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19357>

Original Research Article

Received 5th April 2017
Accepted 1st June 2017
Published 5th June 2017

ABSTRACT

The contamination of agricultural soils by the toxic trace metals arsenic (As), lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn) was investigated in an industrial district in Vietnam. In this district, irrigation agriculture is conducted via channels; additionally, there are two industrial parks on nearby agricultural land. The purpose of the study was to clarify the magnitude and spatial distribution the trace metal concentrations, the source of the trace metals, the difference was in concentration between the two industrial park areas, and the usability of the soils for agriculture. In

*Corresponding author: E-mail: nguyen.van.thinh.999@s.kyushu-u.ac.jp, nvthinh.soil@gmail.com;

this study, eighteen soil samples were taken, and the trace toxic metals in soils were determined using atomic absorption spectrometer. Our results showed that the trace metal concentrations were in the order of Cr > Zn > Pb > Cu > As > Cd for the district. No significant differences were observed between the two park areas in terms of concentration. Cr and Zn concentrations were highest near the factories in the park areas, and the other trace metals were also comparatively high in these areas, demonstrating that the trace metals originated from the factories via wastewater. The correlations observed in the concentrations between the Cd, Pb and Zn, Cr and Zn, and Cu and As suggested that there were several sources of wastewater supplying the trace metals. Concentrations of all trace metals exceeded the permissible level for agricultural soils; therefore, remediation measures are necessary to reduce contamination.

Keywords: Toxic trace metals; soil contamination; industrial waste water; agricultural soils; irrigation water.

1. INTRODUCTION

The contamination of agricultural soils by trace metals from irrigation water mixed with industrial wastewater has been reported frequently since 2000. These reports have been made worldwide from diverse countries including China, Bangladesh, Egypt, Ghana, and India [1–6]. According to these reports, the dominant trace metal contaminant in the soils was different depending on area; however, the concentrations of the trace metals found mostly exceeded the permissible levels for agricultural soils, indicating a serious contamination [7,8]. Furthermore, it was shown that crops grown in contaminated soils were also contaminated with the trace metals [9–11]. Contamination of soils by trace metals can be caused by long-term irrigation, despite the irrigation water being uncontaminated with trace metals [5,12–14]. The trace metal concentrations of the soils were higher on the soil surface and were lower as the soil depth became deeper [15–17].

In Vietnam, soil trace metal contamination in Hanoi City has been reported as follows. Agricultural soils in a factory-concentrated area were contaminated with As, Cd, Cr, and Zn, caused by irrigation water contaminated with industrial waste [18,19]. According to Phuong et al. [20], soils from a paddy field located in a copper casting village were contaminated with Cu, Pb, and Zn. The agriculture soils not only near industrial zones but downstream areas of rivers were also affected by irrigation water that received wastewater from anthropogenic activities upstream [21–23].

Since 2000, industrial parks built outside Hanoi have discharged untreated industrial wastewater into nearby rivers. River water is used for crop irrigation in agricultural lands near factory areas,

and the trace metal contamination is believed to occur in agricultural soils; however, the situation of the contamination is yet to be clarified.

Therefore, in this study, the trace metal contamination of agricultural soils was investigated in a district of Hung Yen Province located near Hanoi City, where two industrial parks are located, with different foundation years and factory composition. Irrigation for agriculture is performed through channels there. The present study investigated five toxic trace metals that potentially contaminated the soil, and was designed with the intention to clarify the magnitude and spatial distribution of the soil trace metal concentrations and the source of the trace metals through the difference in concentrations between the two industrial park areas, and the usability of soils for agricultural purposes, respectively.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study area is an agricultural area belonging to the districts of Van Lam, Yen My and My Hao in Hung Yen Province, which neighbors Hanoi City. Two industrial parks, Pho Noi and Thang Long, are in the study area (referred to as the study district), whose areas are 6 and 2.2 km², respectively. The total population of these areas was 351,340 in 2013, occupying approximately 30% of the provincial population.

The Pho Noi industrial park was built in 2003. Forty-six percent of the factories are mechanical factories, 13% plastic factories, 5% electronic factories, and the remaining industries consist of chemical, textile, food, wood and ceramic factories. In contrast, the Thang Long industrial park was built in 2009 and 38% of the factories

are mechanical, 14% plastic, 14% electronic manufacturing, and the remainder are steel, fluorescent lamp, and electric conductivity equipment factories. Wastewater from the factories is discharged into drains from where the drain water flows into irrigation canals.

According to the Asian Development Bank [24], the average air temperature in the district is 23°C during summer and 16°C during winter, and average annual humidity is 84%. Total annual rainfall is 1584 mm, and the total rainfall in the rainy season reaches 80–85% of the total annual rainfall. The rainy and dry seasons are May–October and November–April, respectively. The topography of Hung Yen Province is flat without hills and mountains, with many rivers where flooding is common in the rainy season.

2.2 Soil Sampling and Chemical Analysis

A total of 18 sites (points) in the district were targeted for soil sampling in paddy fields after considering the distribution of the irrigation canals. The sampling was done in August, 2013

and the locations of the sampling are shown in Fig. 1. The soil collection was done at 5 spots for the respective points. At one spot, 1 kg topsoil (0–20 cm) was collected by using a stainless-steel drill. The soils were stored in plastic bags until use. All soils were air dried, crushed using a ceramic mortar and sieved through a 2 mm sieve to remove gravels and plant residues. Five topsoil samples were thoroughly mixed to be homogeneous. before 500 g soil samples were taken for chemical analysis.

The soil samples prepared above were digested with HNO₃ and H₂O₂ by using the USEPA method 3050B [25] for analyzing the total concentrations of cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn). These analyses were done by flame atomic absorption spectrometer (ANA82, Tokyo Photo Electric Co., Ltd.).

To determine arsenic (As) concentration, a hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometer (280 FS AA, Agilent) was used and soil samples were digested by HNO₃, HCl, HClO₄, H₂SO₄ and HF [26].

Fig. 1. Study area and soil sample sites in industrial zones in Hung Yen Province, Northern Vietnam

2.3 Data Analysis

A one-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to identify the effect of sampling location on the trace metal concentrations, and Welch's t-test was performed to detect the difference in concentrations between the two industrial park areas. Correlation analysis was performed to detect significant correlation between the trace metal concentrations. All statistical analyses were done through Microsoft Excel.

Furthermore, a Smirnov–Grubbs' outlier test was performed to detect the extreme value in the trace metal concentrations. The extreme value may occur due to possible errors in sampling, measurement and/or data recording. The detected extreme values were excluded from the subsequent analysis. To perform the test, SPSS software was used.

3. RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the location map of the study district. Irrigation canals are located from east to

southeast, covering the district. All 18 points for sampling are indicated in Fig. 1. The total target area was 48.5 km².

Fig. 2 shows the trace metal concentrations of Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn and As at each point. The horizontal axis shows the distance from the irrigation water intake to each point along the irrigation canal. The distance for the canal to reach a point from the irrigation water intake was not limited to one (Fig. 1); however, the canal with the shortest distance was adopted. The points around 9–15 km and 18–27 km in the distance belonged to Pho Noi and Thang Long industrial park areas, respectively. Based on Fig. 2, the Cd, As, Cu, and Pb concentrations were less than 100 µg.g⁻¹ at all points, while Zn and Cr concentrations mostly exceeded 100 µg.g⁻¹. At point P1, where the distance from the intake was 0, all concentrations were lower than 111 µg.g⁻¹, and at point P18, where the distance was about 27 km, the concentrations were as low as those at P1. The Cr and Zn concentrations were high with peaks (peak concentrations were higher than 300 and 240 µg.g⁻¹, respectively) at a distance around 12 and 24 km, respectively.

Fig. 2. Trace metal concentrations of Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn and As in relation to the distance from irrigation water intake

Table 1 shows the trace metal concentrations at respective points and its belonging area, descriptive statistics for the concentrations and some other items.

Table 1 shows that the concentrations of Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn, and As ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$) ranged from 1.3–3.5, 45.1–93.2, 46.8–369.0, 29.1–151.3, 93.4–268.3, and 2.3–12.7, respectively. Based on the means, the magnitude of the concentrations was in the order of $\text{Cr} > \text{Zn} > \text{Pb} > \text{Cu} > \text{Cd} > \text{As}$.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows the permissible level for agricultural soils based on the Vietnamese standard [27], as well as the number of sampling points that the permissible level for each trace metal. In Table 1, every kind of trace metal exceeded the permissible level; arsenic (As) concentration exceeded the level ($12 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$) at one point (sample P3), and the Cd, Cr, and Cu concentrations were exceeded at 10 to 13 points out of 18. The maximum exceeding rate of all

concentrations was a little higher than 3 times the permissible level occurred in the Cu concentration.

Table 2 shows the summary of the one way repeated measures ANOVA for the effect of sampling points (sampling locations) on the trace metal concentrations. The p value in Table 2 ($p < 0.05$) shows that the effect of sampling locations was significant, i.e., the trace metal concentrations were different between the sampling locations.

According to Table 1, the concentrations were highest at points 1 and 6, and Cd, Cr, and Zn concentrations were highest in P1. Pb had the highest concentration, and Cu, Zn, and As were the second highest in concentration at P6. Concentrations were generally low in P18. More precisely, Cd and Pb were the lowest, and Cr, Cu, Zn and As were the third lowest in concentrations at P18.

Table 1. Trace metal concentrations at respective sampling points, their descriptive statistics and some other items

Sampling points, belonging area, descriptive statistics and other items		Trace metal concentrations (ppm)					
		Cd	Pb	Cr	Cu	Zn	As
Irrigation water intake	P1	1.3	45.1	85.2	32.4	108.1	4.2
Pho Noi area	P2	1.9	58.2	305.4	43.0	211.6	6.3
	P3	2.0	71.3	264.8	55.8	110.9	4.8
	P4	2.8	65.8	325.2	52.8	126.2	9.6
	P5	2.3	61.4	254.3	34.1	128.3	5.8
	P6	1.6	65.8	296.1	50.2	125.0	5.3
	P7	3.5	84.7	369.0	31.1	268.3	2.3
	P8	2.3	93.2	283.7	63.8	258.5	11.8
	P9	2.6	80.0	285.3	151.3	137.6	11.5
	P10	2.2	57.3	85.2	55.6	126.7	12.7
	P11	2.0	50.1	46.8	42.6	113.8	6.3
	P12	2.2	57.6	188.2	63.7	143.3	7.0
	Thang Long area	P13	2.3	84.8	227.7	29.1	104.5
P14		2.5	84.3	321.9	60.3	125.8	9.3
P15		1.7	53.7	264.0	45.4	122.5	7.3
P16		3.1	81.3	334.7	55.9	242.9	7.6
P17		3.3	79.6	260.0	52.8	93.4	11.4
P18		1.8	49.2	79.9	38.5	110.2	11.3
Max		3.5	93.2	369.0	151.3	268.3	12.7
Min		1.3	45.1	46.8	29.1	93.4	2.3
Mean		2.3	68.0	237.6	53.2	147.6	7.7
Coefficient of variation		0.25	0.21	0.40	0.49	0.37	0.40
Permissible level for agricultural soils		2	70	200	50	200	12
Number of sampling points exceeded the permissible level		12	8	13	10	4	1

Table 2. Summary of the one way repeated measures ANOVA for the effect of sampling points on trace metal concentrations

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	p value
Trace metals	743,991	5	148,798		
Sampling points	67,135	17	3,949	1.99	0.02
Trace metalsxsampling points	168,707	85	1,985		
Total	979,833	107			

The Smirnov–Grubbs' outlier test was performed separately. As a result, the extreme value (extremely high value) was detected in the Zn concentration at P1, P5, P6, and P11 and in the Cu concentration at P4. The extreme value was not detected in Cd, Pb, Cr, and As concentrations at any point.

Table 3 shows the results of Welch's t-test for the concentrations between the two industrial park areas. According to Table 3, p-values ($p > 0.05$) did not show significant differences between the two industrial park areas for the respective concentrations. This result shows that the concentrations were not different between the two park areas.

Table 4 shows the correlation coefficients between the concentrations of Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn, and As. According to Table 4, significant correlations were found between Pb, Cd, and Cr at the 1% significant level, and between Cr and Zn, and Cu and As at the 5% significant level, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Source of the Trace Metals

Most of the trace metal concentrations were higher in the central part of the industrial park

areas than in the irrigation water intake (Table 1, Fig. 2). High concentrations were observed particularly at points 1, 2, 4, 9, 11, and 12 in the central part (Table 1). These points were located near factories (Fig. 1); therefore, the high concentrations were thought to be caused by the entry of the factory-discharged wastewater into the paddy field. As mentioned previously, the district is prone to flooding, and all wastewater from the industrial zone were directly discharged to the irrigation system. Therefore, the entry of heavy metal in soils at these points was probably caused by the flooding of a mix of wastewater and irrigation water and the long-term application this mixture as the source of the irrigation water. The concentration was low at the points away from factories (Fig. 1), indicating that the soil contamination was restricted to near the factory areas.

The extremely high Zn concentration was observed at points 1, 5, 6, and 11 based on the outlier test, indicating that the factories discharging Zn-containing wastewater were located near these points. The extremely high Cu concentration was observed at point 4 by the test, indicating that the factories discharging Cu-containing wastewater were located around this point.

Table 3. Results of Welch's t-test for Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn, and As concentrations between the two industrial parks

Trace metals	Industrial Park	t	d.f.	p value
Cd	Pho Noi	0.52	8.3	0.61
	Thang Long			
Pb	Pho Noi	0.56	8.74	0.59
	Thang Long			
Cr	Pho Noi	0.05	11.21	0.96
	Thang Long			
Cu	Pho Noi	1.06	13.74	0.31
	Thang Long			
Zn	Pho Noi	0.91	10.93	0.38
	Thang Long			
As	Pho Noi	0.51	11.56	0.62
	Thang Long			

Table 4. Correlation coefficients between the trace metal concentrations of Cd, Pb, Cr, Cu, Zn, and As

	Pb	Cr	Cu	Zn	As
Cd	0.69**	0.55*	0.16	0.40	0.15
Pb		0.70**	0.29	0.47	0.09
Cr			0.19	0.51*	-0.14
Cu				0.01	0.51*
Zn					-0.09

* and **: significant at 5 and 1 % levels

Based on the correlation coefficients (Table 4), there were three groups of trace metals, i.e., a group of Cd, Pb, and Cr, a group of Cr and Zn, and a group of Cu and As, based on the significant correlations. The classification of the groups shows that there were several groups of wastewater containing trace metals. In particular, high concentrations of Cr and Zn with significant correlation show that the trace metals may be supplied from the same source of wastewater. Cr and Zn are thought to be discharged from the metal plating processes in a factory, which may be one of the mechanical factories mentioned in the study area, and is present in both industrial parks.

4.2 Difference in the Trace Metal Concentrations between the Two Industrial Park Areas

The trace metal concentrations were in the order of Cr > Zn > Pb > Cu > As > Cd for the respective industrial park areas, based on the average concentrations of the respective areas separately calculated from Table 2. Furthermore, no significant differences were observed in the respective concentrations between the two industrial park areas (Table 3).

Based on these characteristics, the factory composition and foundation year most likely did not affect our results. Here, the absence of any effects from factory composition may have been caused by the concentrations becoming similar with each other after the mixing of wastewaters in irrigation channels in the respective industrial park areas. The absence of effects due to the foundation year (the passage of time), where there is a difference of six years between foundation, may be due to the absorption of trace metals by crops, and/or loss of trace metals by soil washing from flooding. This could decrease the concentrations so that they reached similar levels between the two areas. Usually, the soil trace metal concentrations are considered to increase over time, which has previously been mentioned as a long-term effect of irrigation in trace metal contamination.

4.3 Usability of the Soils for Agricultural Purposes

The Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, and As concentrations exceeded the permissible levels for agricultural soils in Vietnam at 1–13 points out of 18 (Table 1). Although these metal concentrations of some soil samples did not exceed these levels,

but many concentrations were close those presented in Table 1. Despite a lack of permissible levels for Cr soil concentration in Vietnam, Cr concentrations exceeded $200 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ which was the highest permissible range determined by Kabata-Pendias [28] at many points. The soils in this district, contaminated by all trace metals, are therefore inadequate for agricultural soils, and soil decontamination measures are necessary.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn from the study. The magnitude of the trace metal concentrations in the soil samples was in the order of Cr > Zn > Pb > Cu > As > Cd for the study district. Concentrations were highest at the center of the industrial park areas, where there are many factories compared to those in the irrigation water intake, indicating that the trace metals originated from factories within the industrial parks with wastewater. Even inside the district, concentrations were low at points away from the factories, indicating that the contamination was restricted to factory areas.

No significant differences were observed between the two industrial park areas in the concentrations despite differences in foundation year and factory composition between the two industrial park areas.

The trace metal concentrations of the soils exceeded or were close to the permissible levels for agricultural purposes, thus the soils are not adequate for agriculture and some remediation measures, such as soil decontamination, are necessary.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their grateful thanks to Dr. Do Nguyen Hai, Dr. Nguyen Huu Thanh, and Dr. Trinh Quang Huy at the Vietnam National University of Agriculture for providing laboratory equipment in Vietnam.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Liang P, Wu SC, Zhang J, Cao Y, Yu S, Wong MH. The effects of mariculture on

- heavy metal distribution in sediments and cultured fish around the Pearl River Delta region, south China. *Chemosphere*. 2016;148:171–177.
DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.10.110>
2. Rahman SH, Khanam D, Adyel TM, Islam MS, Ahsan MA, Akbor MA. Assessment of heavy metal contamination of agricultural soil around dhaka export processing zone (DEPZ), Bangladesh: Implication of seasonal variation and indices. *appl sci. Molecular Diversity Preservation International*. 2012;2:584–601.
DOI: 10.3390/app2030584
 3. Elbana T, Ramadan M, Gaber HM, Bahnassy MH, Kishk FM, Selim HM. Heavy metals accumulation and spatial distribution in long term wastewater irrigated soils. *J Environ Chem Eng. Elsevier B.V.* 2013;1:925–933.
DOI: 10.1016/j.jece.2013.08.005
 4. Mahmoud EK, Ghoneim AM. Effect of polluted water on soil and plant contamination by heavy metals in El-Mahla El-Kobra, Egypt. *Solid Earth. Copernicus GmbH*. 2016;7:703–711.
DOI: 10.5194/se-7-703-2016
 5. Rattan RK, Datta SP, Chhonkar PK, Suribabu K, Singh AK. Long-term impact of irrigation with sewage effluents on heavy metal content in soils, crops and groundwater - A case study. *Agric Ecosyst Environ*. 2005;109:310–322.
DOI: 10.1016/j.agee.2005.02.025
 6. Kpan JDA, Opoku BK, Gloria A. Heavy metal pollution in soil and water in some selected towns in dunkwa-on-offin district in the central region of ghana as a result of small scale gold mining. *J Agric Chem Environ*. 2014;3:40–47.
DOI: 10.4236/jacen.2014.32006
 7. Omran E-SE. Environmental modelling of heavy metals using pollution indices and multivariate techniques in the soils of Bahr El Baqar, Egypt. *Model Earth Syst Environ*. 2016;2:119.
DOI: 10.1007/s40808-016-0178-7
 8. Omran EE, El Razek AAA. Mapping and screening risk assessment of heavy metals concentrations in soils of the Bahr El-Baker Region, Egypt. *J Soil Sci Environ Manag*. 2012;3:182–195.
DOI: 10.5897/JSEM12.010
 9. Mani D, Kumar C. Biotechnological advances in bioremediation of heavy metals contaminated ecosystems: An overview with special reference to phytoremediation. *Int J Environ Sci Technol*. 2014;11:843–872.
DOI: 10.1007/s13762-013-0299-8
 10. Yadav A, Yadav PK, Shukla PDN. Investigation of heavy metal status in soil and vegetables. *Int J Sci Res Publ*. 2013;3:1–7.
 11. Li P, Wang X, Allinson G, Li X, Xiong X. Risk assessment of heavy metals in soil previously irrigated with industrial wastewater in Shenyang, China. *J Hazard Mater*. 2009;161:516–521.
DOI: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2008.03.130
 12. Qureshi AS, Hussain MI, Ismail S, Khan QM. Evaluating heavy metal accumulation and potential health risks in vegetables irrigated with treated wastewater. *Chemosphere*. 2016;163:54–61.
DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.07.073>
 13. Khan S, Kazi TG, Arain MB, Kolachi NF, Baig JA, Afridi HI, et al. Evaluation of bioavailability and partitioning of aluminum in sediment samples of different ecosystems by modified sequential extraction methods. *Clean - Soil, Air, Water*. 2013;41:808–815.
DOI: 10.1002/clen.201000197
 14. Mapanda F, Mangwayana EN, Nyamangara J, Giller KE. The effect of long-term irrigation using wastewater on heavy metal contents of soils under vegetables in Harare, Zimbabwe. *Agric Ecosyst Environ*. 2005;107:151–165.
DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2004.11.005>
 15. Wei B, Yu J, Dong Y, Yang L, Wang J, Xue Y, et al. Effects of drip irrigation on migration and distribution of heavy metals in soil profile. *Environ Sci Pollut Res*. 2016;23:3632–3640.
DOI: 10.1007/s11356-015-5515-2
 16. Shen F, Liao R, Ali A, Mahar A, Guo D, Li R, et al. Spatial distribution and risk assessment of heavy metals in soil near a Pb/Zn smelter in Feng County, China. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2017;139:254-262.
DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.01.044>
 17. Rajmohan N, Prathapar SA, Jayaprakash M, Nagarajan R. Vertical distribution of heavy metals in soil profile in a seasonally waterlogging agriculture field in Eastern Ganges Basin. *Environ Monit Assess*. 2014;186:5411–5427.
DOI: 10.1007/s10661-014-3790-x

18. Huong NTL, Ohtsubo M, Li L, Higashi T, Kanayama M. Heavy-metal contamination of soil and vegetables in wastewater-irrigated agricultural soil in a suburban area of Hanoi, Vietnam. *Commun Soil Sci Plant Anal.* Taylor & Francis. 2010;41:390–407.
DOI: 10.1080/00103620903494350
19. Thuong NT, Yoneda M, Ikegami M, Takakura M. Source discrimination of heavy metals in sediment and water of to Lich River in Hanoi City using multivariate statistical approaches. *Environ Monit Assess.* 2013;185:8065–8075.
DOI: 10.1007/s10661-013-3155-x
20. Phuong NM, Kang Y, Sakurai K, Iwasaki K, Kien CN, Noi N, et al. Levels and Chemical Forms of Heavy Metals in Soils from Red River Delta, Vietnam. *Water Air Soil Pollut.* 2009;207:319–332.
DOI: 10.1007/s11270-009-0139-0
21. Nguyen Van T, Ozaki A, Nguyen Tho H, Nguyen Duc A, Tran Thi Y, Kurosawa K. Arsenic and heavy metal contamination in soils under different land use in an estuary in Northern Vietnam. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*; 2016.
DOI: 10.3390/ijerph13111091
22. Lewis M, Pryor R, Wilking L. Fate and effects of anthropogenic chemicals in mangrove ecosystems: A review. *Environ Pollut.* Elsevier Ltd. 2011;159:2328–2346.
DOI: 10.1016/j.envpol.2011.04.027
23. Ho HH, Swennen R, Cappuyns V, Vassilieva E, Neyens G, Rajabali M, et al. Geogene Versus Anthropogene Origin of Trace Metals in Sediments in Cua Luc Estuary and Ha Long Bay, Vietnam. *Estuaries and Coasts.* 2013;36:203–219.
DOI: 10.1007/s12237-012-9562-3
24. Asian Development Bank. Comprehensive Socioeconomic Urban Development Project – Viet Tri, Hung Yen, and Dong Dang (Hung Yen). Initial Environmental Examination; 2011.
25. USEPA - United States Environmental Protection Agency. Method 3050B: Acid digestion of sediments, sludges and soils; 1996.
26. SSSA. Methods of soil analysis, Part 3 - chemical methods. Soil Science Society of America, Inc.; 1996.
27. MONRE - Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of The Socialist Republic of Vietnam. scenario of climate change and sea level rise; 2009.
28. Kabata-pendias A. Trace elements in soils and plants. Fourth Edi. CRC Press; 2010.

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Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
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